

IMPLEMENTING "FLIPPED CLASSROOM" METHOD IN TEACHING ENGLISH AND ITS ADVANTAGES

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Annotation: For several years now, a new technique has been popular among advanced teachers — the "Flipped classroom". It is one of the methods of mixed learning. At home, students study theory, and in the classroom they practice practical skills and ask questions to the teacher. In this article I am going to share my opinion on how this method can be implemented in English lessons.

Keywords: *"Flipped classroom", mixed learning, practical skills, flexible classes, video lectures*

Usually, the teacher gives lectures in the classroom at school, while there is very little time left for questions and exercises. How to put all this into practice, you often have to figure it out at home yourself. The study revolves around the classroom, where many students find it difficult to fully assimilate the material. "Most teachers spend their time explaining the material and delivering knowledge, and little time is spent on teaching how to analyze, evaluate and create something. The "Flipped classroom" of learning moves the delivery of knowledge into the student's personal space, and more time is spent on practical skills," explains Jonathan Bergman, one of the authors of the idea of the "Flipped classroom".

"Flipped Classroom" allows students to spend exactly as much time studying a topic as they need to understand it. The student can pause or repeat the lecture recording at any time. It is impossible to repeat the teacher's monologue in the classroom. The traditional education system wants all children to move through the pages of a textbook at the same time, but this is impossible. In the "Flipped classroom, those who understand everything just move on to the next topic, and those who don't spend a little more time understanding. During the classroom, students talk more often with the teacher and with each other, since the whole theory goes to the house. At the same time, lectures are available at any time. They can be viewed online, even if the student is ill for a long time or could not be in class. The same applies to teachers: their schedule is becoming more flexible. I am going to share my experience how this format has changed over the years, why video lectures and podcasts are not a mandatory attribute at all, and how else you

can use flipped classroom. The "Flipped class" should be introduced gradually. We need the students to be ready for it: you can't just dump a new topic into the same video lectures. Most likely, this will lead to the fact that half of the class simply will not do their homework or will not understand what is required of them. It is not necessary to manually record video lectures. It is much more useful when students study the topic at home on their own. Initially, my task was to teach them to get acquainted with some grammar rules in its original form, and not only with the help of adapted texts in textbooks. As a theory, I often give video lectures by famous scientists or teachers. The main thing is that it was not just passive viewing. I try to come up with such tasks so that the guys can ask each other questions. The motivation of the students will not appear immediately. This is creative work, and not just what they heard in class and were immediately able to use in the task. To begin with, you need to give interesting topics that seem to be non-standard, but still allow you to get some information. For example, I offered students to watch video lectures with interesting facts about the rulers. And not necessarily about politics, but, for example, about their personal life or origin. Now you can do tests or text tasks that are checked automatically. It is very convenient and students like it. They can solve this test at any time, look at the result, see the correct answers and their mistakes. I use a web platform where students can upload their assignments, and I can set deadlines and check. The textbook remains a source of information. Despite the fact that I try to give additional materials or primary sources, I work with a textbook in the lesson. This is important because students see how these topics are presented. The textbook is the quintessence of what is happening now. It is adapted to the minimum that you need to know, and also to the age of students. There are such examples when they completely departed from the textbook within the framework of the "Flipped classroom" or studied some paragraphs from the textbook at home. Usually this is either information already structured by the teacher, or video lectures based on textbook materials. Like any teaching method, it has its pros and cons. The teacher should think about how important this or that topic is in the course, how much this knowledge can be "turned over". There are some topics that are simply not suitable for this.

Lecture recordings can be in the form of podcasts, screencasts, videos. It is important that explanations are supported by visual material, for example, a presentation, screenshots or pictures that are shown simultaneously with the speaker or alternate. In order to engage students and use the usual Guided discovery technique, you can include questions during the recording that make

you think, and not just "passively" receive information. To insert questions that will pop up as the video plays, you can use software and web tools that are available. The transition to the inverted class model is a transition from the primacy of the teacher to the primacy of the student. It is a change in the role of a teacher from "sage on the stage" to "guide on the side".

Overall, teachers of English can't completely get away from the usual classroom system. It all depends on what the teacher sees in the "Flipped" learning. If your lessons are not supplemented by anything meaningful from this, then there is simply no great benefit from the "Flipped classroom".

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